

Studies in Physico-Chemical Properties of Caseins. Part VII. Interaction of Caseins with Iodine and Bromine in Solution Phase

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Interaction of casein with aqueous iodine is fairly rapid and involves physical (reversible) adsorption as well as chemical fixation. The amount physically adsorbed appears to correspond to formation of a monomolecular layer on the surface and can be used to estimate surface area of casein. The amount chemically combined may be due to attachment of iodine to tyrosine and other similar groups. The iodinated products containing upto 32% by weight of iodine can be prepared in this manner. Interaction with iodine solution in benzene or carbon tetrachloride is much slower as it takes as long as 26 days for completion instead of just about half an hour as observed in the case of solutions in water. The interaction with aqueous bromine involves not only fixation of bromine but also hydrolysis of bromine yielding hydrogen bromide. The oxygen evolved in the process appears to be taken up by sulphhydryl and methionine groups in casein.

INTERACTION of iodine with proteins has been studied by a number of workers¹⁻⁴ in comparatively recent years in the belief that it would be possible to imitate the activity of the naturally occurring protein thyroglobulin by introducing iodine into other proteins. This belief is based on the finding that the normal thyroid gland itself contains organic iodine as an essential constituent. Since the objective has been to obtain products with as high a degree of iodination as possible, the reagents used and the conditions employed (e.g., mixing of a protein with pulverised iodine and heating the mixture to 100° or treating it in acid media with freshly liberated iodine from a mixture of potassium iodide, potassium iodate and sulphuric acid) have been rather drastic⁵. Iodination of proteins or their constituent amino acids, using iodine in aqueous and non-aqueous solvents, has also been studied^{6,7}. Iodination of casein, however, has not received adequate attention⁸. Since casein is consumed as food in one form or another, any procedure which leads to the incorporation of a controlled amount of iodine should be of great practical interest. Another point of theoretical interest is to explore the possibility of estimating specific surface area of caseins, and may be of other proteins as well, from the amount of iodine adsorbed physically on the surface, as has been done successfully in the case of solid adsorbents, like silica gels⁹, soils¹⁰ and carbon blacks^{11,12}. The present work on interaction of caseins with iodine in aqueous and non-aqueous solvents was undertaken with these objectives in view. The work on interaction with bromine was also taken up to get some comparative data but it was restricted to the determination of the amount fixed irreversibly from aqueous solutions on casein.

Experimental

Materials : Casein was isolated from bovine as well as buffalo milk by the various methods described

in a previous publication¹³. Iodine (E. Merck) solutions were prepared in aqueous potassium iodide (using I⁻/I₂ ratio of 3 : 1) as well as in benzene and carbon tetrachloride (both A.R.). Bromine solutions were prepared in aqueous potassium bromide (using Br⁻/Br₂ ratio of 3 : 1).

Iodination : 0.20 g samples of casein were placed in contact with 40 ml. portions of iodine solutions of a given concentration in 100 ml. pyrex-glass stoppered bottles, wrapped in thick black papers. The contents were shaken for a couple of minutes to affect proper wetting and then allowed to stand in an incubator maintained at 30° for a required interval of time with occasional shaking. An aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid was then withdrawn and examined for fall in concentration of iodine and formation of HI, if any, by the usual volumetric techniques. The suspension, as a whole, including the casein, was then titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate and the fall in concentration of iodine so obtained gave the amount of iodine fixed irreversibly by the casein. This subtracted from the total fall in concentration gave the amount of iodine adsorbed physically i.e., reversibly.

Bromination : 0.20 g samples of casein were placed in contact with 40 ml. portion of 0.1M aqueous bromine (using Br⁻/Br₂ ratio of 3 : 1) with occasional shaking in an incubator maintained at 30° (+0.2°) for 24 hr. These conditions had been worked out in preliminary experiments to get the maximum uptake of bromine. The suspension was filtered and the residue washed repeatedly with hot distilled water to remove any physically adsorbed bromine. The filtrate and the washings were made to a known volume and an aliquot was analysed first for bromine by adding potassium iodide and titrating the iodine liberated against standard sodium thiosulphate in the usual way and then for hydrobromic acid by titrating against standard sodium hydroxide. The

fall in concentration of bromine gave the amount of bromine fixed irreversibly by the casein.

Results and Discussion

The results of a few preliminary experiments which were carried out with one of the samples to standardise the optimum conditions (Fig. 1) show that the contact of casein with 0.7 M aqueous iodine for 30 min results in the maximum uptake of iodine.

Fig. 1. Effect of (a) concentration and (b) time of contact of aqueous iodine on uptake of iodine by casein isolated by Hammarsten method from bovine milk.

The values so obtained in the case of the various caseins are presented in table 1. It is seen, in the first instance, that the iodination can take place to a larger extent in the caseins isolated from cows' milk than in the corresponding samples isolated from buffaloes' milk. Further, the caseins isolated by the rennet and ultracentrifuge methods can take up

more readily in the pH range 5.0 to 10.0, and, generally, rises with the rise in pH value in this range. Our results, broadly speaking, support these conclusions for caseins as well. An additional factor that may be responsible for these differences lies in the calcium contents of the various samples. The caseins separated by the rennet and ultracentrifuge methods retain all the original calcium present in the casein complex while the Hammarsten and Zoller caseins retain only about 80% and 74% respectively, and Vanslyke-Bosworth casein is freed essentially of the whole of the calcium in the course the preparation itself¹⁵. The possibility of formation of calcium-iodine-casein complex, on the analogy of the existence of calcium-phosphorus-casein complex appears to be feasible.

The amounts of iodine taken up physically and reversibly which could be recovered on treatment with aqueous sodium thiosulphate (column 5) were plotted against the corresponding specific surface areas (column 3) as calculated from the composite adsorption isotherms reported in the previous paper¹⁶ of the present series. The values for all the ten samples, irrespective of their source or the method of isolation, appear to fit very well on a reasonably good straight lines, as shown in Fig. 2. This indicates that the extent of physical adsorption of iodine can serve as a good index of surface area of casein. The possibility of using this as a method for determining surface areas of other proteins also needs to be examined.

The slope of the linear relationship plotted in Fig. 2 shows that 0.0078 milligram atoms i.e. 0.0039

TABLE 1—UPTAKE OF IODINE BY DIFFERENT SAMPLES OF CASEIN AFTER 30 MIN CONTACT WITH 0.7M AQUEOUS IODINE AT 30.°

Description of the sample	pH of the sample	Specific surface area of the sample* (m ² /g)	Total amount of iodine taken up by the sample (milligram atom/g)	Amount of iodine physically adsorbed (milligram atom/g)	Amount of iodine chemically combined (milligram atom/g)
<i>Cows' casein isolated by</i>					
Rennet method	6.7	320	7.00	4.06	2.94
Ultracentrifuge method	6.7	420	6.85	4.05	2.80
Hammarsten method	5.1	405	6.30	3.90	2.40
Zoller method	4.9	360	6.03	3.70	2.33
Vanslyke Bosworth method	4.7	330	5.65	3.35	2.30
<i>Buffaloes' casein isolated by</i>					
Rennet method	6.6	310	6.65	3.90	2.75
Ultracentrifuge method	6.6	400	6.55	3.90	2.65
Hammarsten method	5.0	390	5.94	3.84	2.10
Zoller method	4.8	355	5.65	3.52	2.13
Vanslyke Bosworth method	4.7	320	5.41	3.26	2.15

* The specific surface area values reported here are those obtained from composite adsorption isotherms of methanol-benzene mixtures as reported in Part. VI of the present series.

much more iodine than the rest of the samples. The reason for the difference amongst the samples isolated by using different methods appears to lie in their respective pH values. It has been shown¹⁴ that iodination of proteins, in general, can take place

millimoles of iodine can cover an area of 1m² (i.e. 10⁴ cm²) of casein. This shows that the area occupied per iodine molecule is 42.6 Å² which is fairly close to the value 42.0 Å² obtained from limiting adsorption of iodine from aqueous solution on carbon blacks

of known specific surface areas¹⁷. This agreement confirms that physical adsorption of iodine from

Fig. 2. Physisorption of iodine in relation to surface area of casein.

aqueous solution corresponds to formation of a monomolecular layer on the surface of the casein.

The amount of iodine fixed irreversibly appears to be due to chemical combination. It is well known¹⁸ that iodination of proteins, in general, results in the attachment of iodine to the tyrosine groups giving rise to diiodotyrosine, followed by the oxidative coupling of two molecules of diiodotyrosine and the elimination of a side chain¹⁹.

However, in view of some other similar groups and possibility of occurrence of a number of simultaneous reactions, it may not be possible, as has been rightly pointed out by Hughes and Stralle²⁰, to state exactly the amount of iodine which can be introduced in different forms of combination.

The total amount of iodine which gets included into the casein structure by this method amounts, roughly, on average to about 2.5 milligram atoms/g; which corresponds to about 32% by weight. With such a high quantum of iodination, partial denaturation of casein cannot be ruled out. The presence of I⁻ ion is shown²¹ to cause denaturation of proteins in general. As a result of even partial unfolding of the compact casein structure, more reactive groups get exposed and the extent of iodination increases.

In order to get some further insight, the iodination of various caseins was also carried out using iodine solutions in benzene and carbon tetrachloride, so as to avoid the presence of iodide ion. The concentration of the solution in benzene was 0.4 *M* and in carbon tetrachloride 0.2 *M* on account of lower solubility of iodine in this solvent. The temperature was kept constant at 30°, as above. The reaction in each case was found to be extremely slow. The final values were obtained only after 26 days. These are recorded in table 2 for the various samples of casein. The amounts physically adsorbed are seen to be much less than the corresponding values obtained from aqueous solutions. This appears to be partly, at least, due to lower surface tensions of these liquids in comparison to the surface tension of water. The amounts of iodine fixed chemically in most cases, are only about 60% of the values obtained from the aqueous solutions. The advantage of using the non-aqueous solvents lies in the slowness of the reaction (it takes 26 days for the completion of the reaction in benzene and carbon tetrachloride solutions while it takes just 30 min in aqueous solution). Thus the amount of iodine that is desired to be incorporated in casein can easily be controlled.

Interaction with aqueous bromine

The amounts of bromine fixed chemically by the various caseins on treating them with the aqueous solutions under the experimental conditions described earlier in this paper are recorded in table 3. The maximum amount fixed by any of the caseins is about 2.6 mg atom which corresponds to about

TABLE 2—UPTAKE OF IODINE BY VARIOUS SAMPLES OF CASEIN FROM SOLUTIONS IN BENZENE (0.4*M*) AND CARBON TETRACHLORIDE (0.2*M*) AFTER 26 DAYS OF CONTACT AT 30°

Description of the sample	Amount of iodine taken up from its solutions in benzene (milligram atom/g)			Amount of iodine taken up from its solutions in carbon tetrachloride (milligram atom/g)		
	Total	Physically adsorbed	Chemically combined	Total	Physically adsorbed	Chemically combined
<i>Cows' caseins</i>						
Rennet	2.14	0.56	1.58	1.98	0.20	1.78
Ultra-centrifuge	2.32	0.62	1.70	2.00	0.25	1.75
Hammarsten	2.09	0.47	1.62	1.70	0.35	1.35
Zoller	1.98	0.45	1.53	1.64	0.30	1.34
Vanslyke Bosworth	1.90	0.40	1.50	1.65	0.32	1.33
<i>Buffalos' caseins</i>						
Rennet	1.97	0.50	1.47	1.72	0.20	1.52
Ultra-centrifuge	2.12	0.57	1.55	1.76	0.22	1.54
Hammarsten	1.89	0.40	1.49	1.58	0.30	1.28
Zoller	1.86	0.41	1.45	1.50	0.32	1.18
Vanslyke Bosworth	1.86	0.40	1.46	1.50	0.30	1.20

21% of bromine by weight. At the same time there is an appreciable formation of hydrobromic acid (cf. column 4). This is unlike the reaction with aqueous iodine in which case there was no concomitant formation of hydroiodic acid. The formation of hydrobromic acid in such large quantities appears

as intermediates. The total number of sulfhydryl and methionine groups per mole (10^5 g) of casein is reported²³ to be 22. It can be shown by simple calculations that the amounts of oxygen, taken as equivalents of hydrobromic acid formed, are well within the total oxygen requirement of casein for oxidation of these groups.

TABLE 3—AMOUNTS OF BROMINE FIXED BY THE VARIOUS SAMPLES OF CASEIN AFTER 24 HR CONTACT WITH 0.1M AQUEOUS BROMINE AT 30°

Description of the sample	pH of the sample	Bromine fixed (milligram atom/g)	Hydrobromic acid formed (meq/g)
<i>Cows' caseins</i>			
Rennet	6.7	2.62	5.09
Ultracentrifuge	6.7	2.35	5.00
Hammarsten	5.1	1.50	6.42
Zoller	4.9	1.56	6.53
Vanslyke Bosworth	4.7	1.31	6.61
<i>Buffalos' caseins</i>			
Rennet	6.6	2.15	4.89
Ultracentrifuge	6.6	2.00	4.92
Hammarsten	5.0	1.34	5.43
Zoller	4.8	1.51	5.67
Vanslyke Bosworth	4.7	1.45	6.83

to be due to hydrolysis of bromine evolving oxygen. This is not unexpected since the oxidation potential of aqueous bromine is much higher than that of aqueous iodine. However, no oxygen was evolved as such. This was checked by analysing the gas above the reaction mixture in the bottle. It appears that the oxygen liberated during the reaction is taken up by the sulfhydryl and methionine groups in casein. In this connection it may be noted that Conslor, Gordon and Marin²² showed that treatment of wool by aqueous bromine as well as hydrogen peroxide results in the oxidation of these groups leading to the formation of sulphonic and sulphoxides

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